

EVALUATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN OBESITY AND GINGIVAL CREVICULAR FLUID RESISTIN LEVEL IN PERIODONTITIS PATIENTS

ABD-ELKAREEM MAHMOUD AHMED ABD-ELBAKI

BDS Faculty of Dentistry, AL-Azhar University (Assiut branch) Dental Practitioner, Ministry of Health.

BAHAA MOHAMMED BADR

Department of Medical Microbiology and Immunology, Faculty of Dentistry, Zarqa University, Zarqa, Jordan.
Faculty of Medicine, Al-Azhar University (Assiut branch), Assiut, Egypt.

KHALID MOHAMED AFIFY EL RAHAWAY

Department of Oral Pathology, Faculty of Dentistry, Al-Azhar University (Assiut branch), Assiut, Egypt.

ABDULLAH IBRAHIM ABD RABBOUH ALI

Department of Oral medicine, Periodontology, Oral diagnosis and Dental radiology Faculty of Dentistry, Al-Azhar University (Assiut branch), Assiut, Egypt.

IBRAHIM HAMMAD IBRAHIM

Department of Oral medicine, Periodontology, Oral diagnosis and Dental radiology Faculty of Dentistry, Al-Azhar University (Assiut branch), Assiut, Egypt.

Abstract

Background: Resistin was discovered in mice in 2001 and the reason for this name due to its ability to resist or interfere with insulin action. The increase in adipose tissue, which is a characteristic of obesity, is a significant source of several pro-inflammatory cytokines such as resistin. Periodontitis has a strong relation with obesity and diabetes, and obese subjects have been proven to be at risk for acquiring the disease. **Objective:** This trial was conducted to assess the relationship between obesity and resistin levels in gingival crevicular fluid in cases with periodontitis as well as assess the effect of non-surgical periodontal intervention on resistin levels by ELISA. **Materials and Methods:** This randomized controlled clinical trial was performed on 60 participants (30 periodontitis & 30 healthy) of both sexes divided into four equal groups according to body mass index (BMI) from examination of 270 individuals were selected. GCF level of resistin was assessed at base line for healthy groups and at base line, 2 weeks, 1 and 3 months after conventional periodontal treatment for periodontitis groups. **Results:** A significant increase in GCF resistin level in obese when compared with normal weight individuals which being much a higher value in obese periodontitis patients. **Conclusions:** A close relationship between GCF resistin level, periodontitis and obesity was found in this study. GCF resistin level in periodontal disease may be used as alternative biomarker to identify subjects at risk for periodontitis.

Keywords: Periodontitis, Obesity, Resistin.

INTRODUCTION

Periodontitis is a common chronic inflammatory disease bacterially induced and propagated by host response⁽¹⁾. The increased synthesis and release of inflammatory mediators and proteases as a result of the induced host inflammatory response results in extracellular matrix breakdown and bone loss⁽²⁾.

Lipopolysaccharides (LPS) generated by periodontal infections have been demonstrated to promote the expression of the resistin gene in macrophages via a cascade including the generation of proinflammatory mediators ^(3,4).

Resistin, a protein rich in cysteine, was initially hypothesized to be related to diabetes and obesity in rats. Resistin considered a pro-inflammatory mediator plays a regulatory role in multiple chronic inflammatory diseases, infectious diseases, metabolic diseases, and cancer in human. Resistin expressed in adipocytes and immune cells ⁽⁵⁾.

In periodontal disease, resistin modulates inflammation and may be used as alternative measure to identify individuals at risk for periodontitis ⁽⁶⁾. There is evidence of a three-way association between periodontitis, diabetes, and obesity ⁽⁷⁾.

The increase in adipose tissue, which is a characteristic of obesity, is a significant source of several pro-inflammatory cytokines such as resistin ⁽⁸⁾. Periodontitis has a strong relation with obesity and diabetes, and obese subjects have been proven to be at risk for acquiring the disease. A positive correlation between body mass index with periodontal attachment loss was found. However, the biological mechanisms that relate this relationship obesity remains unknown ⁽⁹⁾.

This trial was conducted to assess the relationship between obesity and resistin levels in gingival crevicular fluid in cases with periodontitis as well as assess the effect of non-surgical periodontal intervention on resistin levels by ELISA.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Patient Selection

This randomized controlled clinical trial was carried out on 60 individuals (30 healthy & 30 periodontitis) cases with grade A, stage I & II periodontitis, with probing pocket depth ≤ 5 mm, CAL 1-4 mm and mostly horizontally radiographic bone loss $\leq 33\%$ at coronal third⁽¹⁰⁾, aged from (23-47) with mean age (32.58 \pm 6.5) of both sexes (32 females and 28 males). All cases were recruited from the cases attended the Outpatient Clinic, Oral Medicine and Periodontology Department, Faculty of Dental Medicine, Al-Azhar University, Assiut Branch.

The entry criteria were: (1) Systemic health non-compromised individuals; (2) No prior periodontal intervention in the preceding six months; (3) Patients not received non-steroidal anti-inflammatory or antibiotics for at least 3 months prior to beginning of study; (4) Non-smokers; (5) Females being non-pregnant.

Ethical Issues

This trial obtained approval from the ethical committee Faculties of dental medicine, Al-Azhar University, Assiut Branch. (approval AUAREC202300010-2).

Obesity Assessment

Participants were classified into obese and normal weight groups according to BMI scale, which can be obtained by dividing the total body weight (kg) by the square of the height (m), as a substitute of the total body fat measure ⁽¹¹⁾, obesity equals BMI value of $\geq 30 \text{Kg/m}^2$ ⁽¹²⁾.

Patients Grouping and Randomization

After calculation of BMI, the included periodontitis and healthy individuals were randomly classified into the following four groups:

Group I: 15 obese patients with grade A, stage I & II periodontitis who underwent non-surgical periodontal intervention.

Group II: 15 normal weights patients with grade A, stage I & II periodontitis who underwent non-surgical periodontal intervention.

Group III: 15 obese periodontally healthy individuals.

Group IV: 15 normal weight periodontally healthy individuals.

Gingival Crevicular Fluid Sample Collection

All GCF samples were taken by the same standardized protocol for sampling procedure.

Samples were taken from the sites with the highest probing depth ≤ 5 mm and CAL ≤ 4 mm

The selected sites and adjacent teeth were isolated with cotton rolls prior sampling, supragingival plaque was carefully removed without touching the marginal gingiva to avoid samples' contamination. The crevicular site was then dried gently with an air syringe.

Paper point ISO #30 taper 0.02 mm/mm (Co. Roeko, Langenau, Germany) was inserted slowly to the maximum depth of the periodontal pocket with dental tweezers. The paper point was kept in place for 30 sec, after which it was gently withdrawn without touching surrounding unrelated tissues and points contaminated with blood were discarded then transferred to a sterile Eppendorf tube containing a phosphate buffer saline (PBS) and frozen until analysis at -80°C by commercially available ELISA test (Sunred Biological Technology Co., Ltd-China Shanghai).

Biochemical Evaluation

Level of GCF resistin was assessed at base line for healthy groups and at base line, 2 weeks, 1 and 3 months after treatment for periodontitis groups.

Periodontal intervention

All periodontitis cases were subjected to full-mouth scaling and root planing without the use of adjunct treatment.

RESULTS

I- Differences in the BMI among the studied groups at baseline

a significant variation between groups in the mean BMI ($p < 0.001$) was found. Table (1)

Table 1: Comparison between Groups & Resistin Level between Groups at Baseline & Correlation between Resistin Level and BMI among Cases

(Mean \pm SD)	BMI	BE	BE	P-value	Resistin Level	P-value
		Rho	P-value			
Group I	33.76 \pm 1.5	0.109	= 0.182	I vs. II < 0.001	14.34 \pm 1.7	I vs. II = 0.035
Group II	22.63 \pm 1.5	0.354	= 0.048	I vs. III = 0.476	13.30 \pm 0.5	I vs. III < 0.001
Group III	34.24 \pm 1.4	-0.195	= 0.095	I vs. IV < 0.001	9.05 \pm 0.6	I vs. IV < 0.00
Group IV	22.18 \pm 1.5	0.406	= 0.026	II vs. III < 0.001	7.62 \pm 0.9	II vs. III < 0.001
				II vs. IV = 0.506		II vs. IV < 0.001
				III vs. IV < 0.001		III vs. IV = 0.005
P-value		0.277	= 0.042			< 0.001

II. Biochemical Results

A- Difference in resistin level (ng/ml) among studied groups at baseline.

a significant variation in the mean of resistin level between groups ($p < 0.001$) was reported.

For pairwise comparisons, there was significant higher resistin level in group I when compared with group II, group III and group IV. Moreover, a statistically significant higher resistin level was found in group II compared with group III and group IV. Finally, a significantly higher resistin level was found in group III compared with group IV. Table(1)

B- Difference in the resistin level (ng/ml) among the studied groups at evaluation period

A significant variation in the resistin level over time from baseline to 3 months in group I and group II was reported, which appeared to be a higher in group I when in comparison with group II (group I had lower mean value level). However, when comparing both groups, no significant variation between the two groups at baseline, 2 weeks and at 1 month and significant difference observed only at 3 months. Table (2)

Table 2: Comparison of resistin (ng/ml) between groups over time

(Mean \pm SD)	Group I (n=15)	P-value	Group II (n=15)	P-value	P-value
• Baseline (1)	14.34 \pm 1.7	1 vs. 2 = 0.011	13.30 \pm 0.5	1 vs. 2 = 0.002	= 0.090
• 2-weeks (2)	11.98 \pm 0.9	1 vs. 3 = 0.004	12.18 \pm 1.1	1 vs. 3 < 0.001	= 0.650
• 1-month (3)	11.40 \pm 1.1	1 vs. 4 < 0.001	11.35 \pm 1.1	1 vs. 4 < 0.001	= 0.916
• 3-months (4)	8.88 \pm 0.5	2 vs. 3 = 0.092	7.94 \pm 1.2	2 vs. 3 = 0.002	= 0.036
		2 vs. 4 < 0.001		2 vs. 4 < 0.001	
		3 vs. 4 < 0.001		3 vs. 4 < 0.001	
P-value	< 0.001		< 0.001		P=0.106

C- Correlation between resistin level and BMI.

For the total sample, there was significant ($p = 0.042$) positive moderate correlation ($\rho = 0.277$) i.e., with increase in the BMI, there was increase in the resistin level. This was also proved in groups II and IV ($\rho = 0.354$ and 0.406 , $p = 0.048$ and 0.026). On the other hand, insignificant ($p = 0.182$ and 0.095) positive and negative mild correlation ($\rho = 0.109$ and 0.195) was found between resistin level and BMI in groups III and I. Table (1)

DISCUSSION

Periodontitis is a chronic inflammatory reaction to the accumulated calculus and microbial plaque on the surface of the tooth. Toxic chemicals generated by microorganisms trigger the production of inflammatory mediators, resulting in periodontal tissue destruction mediated by the host. ⁽¹³⁾.

Although numerous pro-inflammatory cytokines and inflammatory mediators serve as biomarkers for periodontal disease, the recently discovered resistin, which is an adipokine cysteine-rich protein, is expressed at a very low level in adipocytes and at a higher level in circulating inflammatory immune cells. These resistin are primarily associated with diabetes and obesity. Later, it was discovered to have a role in chronic periodontitis by stimulating the production and release of TNF- and IL-12 as a proinflammatory molecule ^(7,14).

Due to an excessive buildup of body fat, adipose tissue secretes bioactive molecules known as adipocytokines, which are associated with elevated resistin levels in obese individuals ⁽¹⁵⁾. Periodontitis tends to afflict obese persons more frequently and severely than those of normal weight ⁽¹⁶⁾. So, the present research was designed as randomized controlled clinical trial to evaluate the relationship between obesity and GCF resistin levels in periodontitis patients as well as assess the effect of non-surgical periodontal intervention on resistin levels using ELISA.

There are many ways of collecting GCF include paper strips, capillary tubes, paper points and gingival washing. In our study, paper points (paper points size # 30 and for 30 seconds) were used for sampling, because they are a relatively simple, time efficient and can be used to assay selected sites with minimal tissue trauma, but this has a difficulty in standardization ⁽¹⁷⁾.

Patients included in this study are categorized into obese and normal weight according to BMI, which can be obtained by dividing the total body weight (kg) by the square of the height (m), as a substitute of the total body fat measure ⁽¹¹⁾. So, obesity equals BMI value of $\geq 30 \text{Kg/m}^2$ ⁽¹²⁾.

Nonsurgical periodontal treatment is the cornerstone of periodontal therapy, the first suggested strategy for controlling periodontal infection, and is currently regarded as the gold standard against which all other treatment modalities are measured ⁽¹⁸⁾. Previous

studies found that scaling and root planning with oral hygiene instruction are considered effective methods in treatment of mild to moderate periodontitis cases^(19,20).

Biochemically with regard to GCF resistin level, which used as a marker in the current trial demonstrate that the mean baseline value was found to be higher in obese periodontitis cases (group I) (14.43 ± 1.7) followed by periodontitis patients with normal weight (group II) (13.3 ± 0.5 , $p = 0.035$), compared with obese periodontally healthy individuals (group III) (9.05 ± 0.6 , $p < 0.001$) and normal weight periodontally healthy individuals (group IV) (7.62 ± 0.9 , $p < 0.001$). These results indicate that obesity and periodontitis separately or jointly modify the GCF resistin levels, primarily in favor of pro-inflammation, as described in a prior study with comparable results⁽²¹⁾.

When comparing baseline resistin level in all groups results of the present research found a statistically significant variation in the GCF concentration of resistin in periodontally healthy group (III & IV) when compared with periodontitis groups (I & II). These finding is in agreement with the result obtained by previous studies in which the level of resistin was evaluated from serum samples⁽²²⁾. This increase in resistin level could be attributed to first, the fact that resistin is mainly expressed from polymorphonuclear leukocytes and macrophages in inflammatory conditions as periodontitis⁽²³⁾. Second, with lipopolysaccharide stimulation, putative periodontal pathogens such as *p.gingivalis* lead to increase resistin levels in GCF⁽²⁴⁾.

In the present trial, levels of GCF resistin were up regulated in both groups with periodontitis (group I and II) (14.43 and 13.3 ng/dl) suggesting that irrespective of obesity, periodontal inflammation may modify GCF levels of this proinflammatory marker. One explanation could be that, rather than adipocytes, macrophages and peripheral mononuclear cells may produce resistin in humans, as this cytokine is connected with the stimulation of the inflammatory process and IL-6 expression by these cells.⁽²⁵⁾

The current trial showed decrease in the level of resistin measurement after scaling and root planning. On intergroup comparison of resistin levels at baseline in all groups, no significant variations between the first two groups at baseline, 2 weeks and at 1 month ($p=0.090$, 0.650 and 0.916) was reported. However, a significant variation ($p = 0.036$) was reported at 3 months between the two groups. This could be due to the fact that the optimal time interval for evaluating the efficacy of nonsurgical periodontal treatment that led to a significant reduction in pro-inflammatory mediators, including resistin, and tissue healing is around three months⁽²⁶⁾. This resolution of the inflammation in turn reduces the level of resistin and hence biochemical analysis was done through a period of 3 months following SRP.

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تقييم العلاقة بين السمنة ومستوي ريزيستين في السائل اللثوي لمرضى التهاب الانسجة الحول سنينة
(دراسة بيو كيميائية)

- 1- عبد الكريم محمود احمد عبد الباقي بكالوريوس طب وجراحة الفم والأسنان 2013 - كلية طب الأسنان جامعة الأزهر (فرع أسيوط) - طبيب اسنان بوزارة الصحة
- 2- خالد محمد عفيفي الرهاوى أستاذ مساعد بقسم أمراض الفم والأسنان كلية طب الأسنان - جامعة الأزهر (فرع أسيوط)
- 3- إبراهيم حماد إبراهيم مدرس بقسم طب الفم وأمراض اللثة وتشخيص الفم وأشعه الأسنان كلية طب الأسنان - جامعة الأزهر (فرع أسيوط)
- 4- بهاء محمد بدر مدرس الميكروبيولوجيا الطبية والمناعة كلية الطب - جامعة الأزهر (فرع أسيوط)

الهدف من الدراسة:

لتقييم العلاقة بين السمنة ومستوي الريزستين في السائل اللثوي في مرضى التهاب الانسجة حول السنينة وكذلك تقييم تأثير العلاج اللثوي غير الجراحي على مستوى الريزستين باستخدام اختبار الامتصاص المناعي المرتبط.

التصنيف:

صممت هذه الدراسة على أنها تجربة سريرية عشوائية مضبوطة أجريت على ستين مشاركاً (30 مريضاً و 30 صحيحاً) من كلا الجنسين مقسمة إلى أربع مجموعات متساوية وفقاً لمؤشر كتلة الجسم (BMI) من فحص 270 فرداً. تم تقييم مستوى الريزستين في السائل اللثوي عند خط الأساس للمجموعات الصحيحة. وعند خط الأساس وبعد أسبوعين وشهر واحد و 3 أشهر بعد العلاج التقليدي للثة لمجموعات مرضى التهاب الانسجة حول السنينة.

النتائج:

زيادة ملحوظة في مستوى الريزستين السائل اللثوي في السمنة بالمقارنة مع الأفراد ذوي الوزن الطبيعي والتي تكون ذات قيمة أعلى بكثير في مرضى التهاب الانسجة حول السنية.

الخلاصة:

وجد في هذه الدراسة , علاقة وثيقة بين مستوى الريزستين في السائل اللثوي والتهاب الانسجة حول السنية والسمنة. يمكن استخدام مستوى الريزستين في السائل اللثوي في أمراض اللثة كمؤشر حيوي بديل لتحديد الأشخاص المعرضين لخطر الإصابة بالتهاب الانسجة حول السنية.